

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF THE QUALITY OF RE-PROSTHETICS WITH COMPLETE REMOVABLE DENTURES USING CHEWING TESTS

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Abstract

Repeated prosthetics with complete removable plate dentures, along with primary prosthetics in the clinic of orthopedic dentistry, is one of the pressing problems of modern dentistry. At the same time, this type of prosthetics in many cases turns out to be ineffective or ineffective, although, at first glance, the treatment was carried out with the same prosthetic designs. Therefore, the methodological basis for orthopedic treatment of patients with complete absence of teeth and the study of the masticatory apparatus should be a systematic approach. Its principles formed the basis for the development of a promising direction in the rehabilitation of this category of patients - the production of complete removable dentures using the technique of duplicating old dentures.

Keywords: removable plate denture, repeated prosthetics, chewing tests.

The purpose of the study is to analyze, using functional chewing tests, the features of the functioning of the masticatory system of patients with complete absence of teeth during the period of adaptation to complete removable dentures made using the traditional method and using the duplication technique.

Material and methods.

Patients who received dental orthopedic care for repeated prosthetics were divided into two equal groups. The first (control) - patients who were treated using the traditional method of manufacturing complete removable dentures. The second (experienced) - patients who were offered and carried out a technique for duplicating complete removable dentures. In order to determine the chewing time and chewing efficiency in patients of the two groups before repeated prosthetics, as well as after repeated orthopedic treatment, a chewing test was used according to I.S. Rubinov [3]. Chewing time, chewing efficiency and chewing index [1] were determined by us in all patients of two groups before re-prosthetics, as well as on the day of application, 1 month, 6 months, 1 year, 2 and 3 years after it. The obtained data were processed statistically using the statistical package SPSS 11.0 for Windows.

Results and discussion.

Analyzing the chewing time data in patients who had repeated dentures using standard methods before and after treatment, a significant increase in this indicator is clearly noted one day after the application of dentures: 44.83 ± 2.97 and 49.92 ± 3.02 s, respectively. 1 month after prosthetics, chewing time also does not reach its previous value of 46.62 ± 3.01 s. These data tell us that patients spend more muscle effort chewing almonds, the chewing period increases, and the time of

adaptation to newly manufactured dentures lengthens. Comparing chewing time at later periods (6 months, 1 year, 2 years), we note a decrease in indicators and the achievement of minimum values of 32.66 ± 2.83 s 1 year after orthopedic care. After three years of using dentures, chewing time approaches the initial data of 43.62 ± 2.94 s. In patients who received repeated dentures using our proposed method of duplicating complete removable dentures, there was no increase in the time of chewing 0.8 g of almonds after 24 hours and 1 month, but on the contrary, it decreased, although slightly, 41.96 ± 3.02 and respectively. 40.13 ± 3.09 s, before treatment 42.66 ± 0.9 s. The patients did not experience any problems with chewing food or discomfort when wearing prostheses, which were structurally minimally different from previously manufactured ones. At later periods of using prostheses, there was also a decrease in this indicator with a minimum value 1 year after prosthetics of 30.48 ± 2.91 s, which indicates that the patients have fully adapted to the prostheses and are using them successfully. After 3 years, chewing time increased again to 41.39 ± 3.09 s. Examining the following functional indicator - chewing efficiency, in patients whose dentures during repeated prosthetics were made using standard methods, there was a maximum decrease in values after 1 day - $42.69 \pm 0.82\%$ and after 1 month - $44.85 \pm 0.91\%$ after treatment, before prosthetics this figure was $46.42 \pm 0.87\%$. This group reaches its maximum chewing efficiency of $58.70 \pm 0.94\%$ 1 year after the application of dentures. After three years of using prostheses, this figure decreases to the values that were before treatment - $46.44 \pm 0.91\%$. The dynamics of chewing efficiency in pa-

tients who received repeated dentures using the technique of duplicating old complete removable dentures differs from the control group. After the first day after prosthetics, this figure steadily increases and reaches a maximum ($64.81 \pm 1.05\%$) 1 year after orthopedic care. The increase in chewing efficiency from the first day of using newly made dentures tells us about the good quality of the dentures and the absence of problems of adaptation to them. Changes in the chewing index were also different in the control and experimental groups. If in patients of the control group the chewing index before treatment was 10.48 ± 0.84 mg/s, then after treatment according to the standard method it began to decrease, a day later - 8.32 ± 0.57 mg/s, and after 1 month - 9.52 ± 0.69 mg/s. We see that patients experienced problems using prostheses, the manufacture of which did not take into account the individual characteristics of previous prostheses. In the experimental group, the chewing index after 24 hours and the 1st month of using complete removable dentures did not decrease, but increased, in contrast to the data obtained in the control group; before treatment, the indicator was 12.18 ± 0.90 mg/s, after 1 day 12.76 ± 0.94 mg/s and after 1 month

14.56 ± 1.12 mg/s. The chewing index reached its maximum values after the first year of using dentures in both groups; after 3 years the index approached the initial values. Therefore, the next re-prosthetics should be carried out after three years of using complete removable dentures.

Conclusion.

There is a need for wider use of the technique of duplicating complete removable dentures during repeated prosthetics in order to improve the quality and efficiency of orthopedic care for patients with complete loss of teeth. The period for repeated prosthetics in the case of complete absence of teeth should not exceed 3 years.

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